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The Growth and Yield of Four Soybean Varieties in Coastal Land under Various Doses of Vermicompost

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Abstract

A scarcity of productive land for agricultural cultivation constraints increasing soybean production in Indonesia. Coastal land is the potential for the agricultural area to increase soybean production. However, Soybean cultivation in coastal lands is hindered by low soil fertility. To enhance soybean yield in coastal regions, vermicomposting and growing superior varieties of soybeans is promising. This study aimed to discover the best cultivars and vermicompost doses for soybean growth and yield in a coastal area. The study was conducted from July to November 2020 at 2 m above sea level in Lempuing Village, Kuala Alam, Ratu Agung SubDistrict, Bengkulu City, Indonesia. The experiment used a Completely Randomized Block Design (RCBD) with two factors. The first factor was soybean varieties, which included the soybean cultivar of Detap 1, Devon 1, Gepak Kuning, and Dering 1. The second factor was the vermicompost dose, consisted of control (no vermicompost), vermicompost at 5, 10, and 15 ton/ha. The experiment showed that the Devon 1 variety fertilized with vermicompost at 5 tons/ha exhibited the longest soybean harvest time, followed by the Gepak Kuning variety fertilized with vermicompost at 10 ton/ha. The highest soybean yields were produced from the Gepak Kuning variety, followed by Dering 1, Detap 1, and Devon 1. Applying vermicompost prolongs the harvest time for soybeans grown in coastal areas.

Key words: coastal area, coastal land, sandy soil, soybean varieties, vermicompost

INTRODUCTION

Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) is Indonesia's primary vegetable protein source and is commonly used for industrial, food, and feed purposes. The shortage of fertile land in Indonesia is an obstacle to increasing soybean production; hence expanded soybean production targets marginal land, including coastal land. Bengkulu Province has a 525-kilometer-long coastline (Bengkulu Provincial Government, 2015). The soil qualities of coastal areas are often unstable, with low soil moisture, high evapotranspiration, high salinity, and low organic matter content (Sumardi, 2008). Coastal land also has a low Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC), C-organic, and water holding capacity (Rajiman et al., 2008; Cornell et al., 2003). High sand content in this soil causes low water-holding capacity and soil moisture rapidly decreases (Sitorus et al., 2008).

Using vermicompost in coastal areas is intended to improve the soil structure and increase water-holding capacity, allowing plants to thrive. Vermicompost is a fertilizer produced by composting organic waste with earthworms. This organic fertilizer enhances the soil physical, chemical, and biological

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properties (Kusnadi, 2000). Previous studies confirmed that vermicompost substantially increased soil nitrate and phosphorous (Muktamar et al., 2020; Muktamar et al., 2022). Because vermicompost has a faster effect and requires fewer dosages, it is more efficient than other organic fertilizers. Hence, using vermicompost reduces the need for synthetic fertilizers (Visvanathan et al., 2005).

Vermicompost promotes plant growth and the development of mycorrhizal symbiosis. Vermicompost contains 34.5 % C, 1.8 % N, 1.1 % P, 1.5 % K, 3.6 % Ca, 1.5 % Mg, Fe 1025.1 mg/kg, Zn 206.8 mg/kg, 1028.6 mg/kg, pH 5.7, exchange capacity 54.9 mg /kg and an electrical conductivity of 22.7 μ S cm (Nusantara et al., 2010). Thus, applying vermicompost supplies nutrients to the soil and increases soil fertility. The application of vermicompost significantly increases the nutrient uptake and yield of maize and sweet corn (Muktamar et al., 2017). Plant development depends on the vermicompost dosage and other factors, including planting location and plant variety.

It is essential to determine the soybean cultivars to achieve their maximum yield by cultivating them at suitable environmental conditions. Plant varieties are imperative in soybean production since high yields mainly depend on genetic potential and the growing environment (Caldwell et al., 2005; Hartman et al., 2011). Superior soybean cultivars will only attain their full potential in a suitable growing environment.

The utilization of superior varieties determines soybean production. Soybean Variety Detap 1 was released in 2017 with a harvest period of around 78 days, a yield potential of up to 2.70 tons/ha, and highly unbroken ripe pods. The Devon 1 variety has a harvest period of 83 days with a yield potential of up to 2.75 ton/ha. Gepak Kuning and Dering 1 variety are superior quality soybeans that are early maturing with a harvest age of 70-80 days. This study aimed to determine the best varieties and vermicompost dose for the growth and yield of soybean in the coastal area.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research was carried out from July to November 2020 in Lempuing Village, Kuala Alam, Ratu Agung SubDistrict, Bengkulu City, Indonesia, at 2 meters above sea level. The design was a Completely Randomized Block Design (RCBD) with two factors. The first factor was soybean varieties, consisting of V1 = Detap 1, V2 = Devon 1, V3= Gepak Kuning, and V4= Dering 1. The second factor was the dose of vermicompost, consisting of D0= Without Vermicompost, D1 = Vermicompost 5 ton/ha, D2 = Vermicompost 10 ton/ha, and D3 = Vermicompost 15 ton/ha. Each combination was repeated three times. Plot was constructed with 1 m x 1.5 m (l x w). Seeds were planted with 25 cm x 25 cm spacing and 24 plants per experimental plot. Initial soil analysis was carried out to determine C-organic content, pH, total N, available P, and exchangeable K. Vermicompost was also analyzed for C-organic (%), C/N ratio, N (%), P (%), and K (%).

According to the treatment, Vermicompost was applied one week before planting by spreading over the soil's surface. Soybean seeds were sown at a depth of 3cm-4cm and a 25 x 25 cm spacing, and in each planting hole applied, two granules of carbofuran were coated with *Rhizobium* sp bacteria to prevent pest infestation. A week after planting, NPK compound fertilizer was applied at a rate of 1.2 g/plant or 200 kg/ha. Plant thinning was conducted one week after planting (WAP) by leaving the healthier seedling. Plants were watered every day when necessary to make the soil moist. Weeds were controlled manually, and disease was controlled using Profenofos insecticide at the recommended dosage. Soybean was harvested after 95% of the pods turned brown and yellowish-brown stems.

Plant height (cm), leaves number, branches number, pods and seeds number, seed weight (g/tan), the weight of 100 seeds (g), fresh and dry shoot weight (g), root fresh and dry weight (g), harvest age (days), and pod/plot weight (g) were recorded. The rainfall, temperature, and humidity data were obtained from the Meteorology, Climatology, and Geophysics Agency of Bengkulu City. Data were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at a 5% level. The separation of treatment means was analyzed using LSD at the 5% level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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Initial soil analysis indicated that the soil was classified as sand with C-organic 6.13% (very high), pH 5.93 (slightly acidic), total-N 0.04% (very low), available-P 19.84 ppm (very high), exchangeable K 0.13 cmol(+)/kg (low), exchangeable Na 0.08 cmol(+)/kg (very low), CEC 16.76 cmol(+)/kg (low), and a sand, silt, and clay content was 91.32%, 1.95% and 6.73%, respectively. The results suggest that the experimental site was infertile soil with a very high content of sand, indicating the coastal environment. The vermicompost contains 26.16% organic-C, pH 7.31, N 1.65%, C/N ratio 15.87, P 1.08%, K 2.04%, and water content 27.04 %.

Soybean can grow well at an altitude of up to 500 meters above sea level in tropical and subtropical climates. Soybeans require rainfall of 120-135 mm/month, air temperature between 23-26 °C, and a soil pH of 5.5 - 7.5. (Andayanie, 2016). During the study, from July to August 2020, the rainfall is sufficient for soybean growth, allowing it to grow well from planting to 5 weeks after planting. So did the soil pH.

Broadleaf weeds and grasses grew in nearly every plot during the study. These weeds could become hosts of soybeans pests. Caterpillars (*Spodoptera farugiferda*), grasshoppers (*Caelifera*), ladybugs (*Hemiptera*), and stink bugs (*Leptocorisa oratorios*). are among the pests that infest soybeans. Pests were chemically controlled using pesticides with the active ingredient of Profenofos 500g/l.

Analysis of Variance

The study showed an interaction effect between soybean varieties and the application of vermicompost fertilizer during the soybean harvest period. The total number of pods, empty pods, the weight of 100 seeds, and the harvest age significantly differed among soybean varieties. On the other hand, vermicompost applied at different doses had a significant effect on the harvest period but had no significant effect on other variables (Table 1)

Table 1.

Variable	F-calc			CV	CV ^t
	Interaction	Varieties	Vermicompost		
Plant height	1,668 ns	1,590 ns	1,428 ns	18,42	
Leaves number	0,636 ns	1,239 ns	0,613 ns	31,24	
Branch number	0,610 ns	2,454 ns	0,399 ns	38,77	17,82
Productive branch number ^t	0,544 ns	2,960 ns	0,581 ns	73,32	23,23
Pods number	0,662 ns	3,007 *	0,398 ns	75,07	35,67
Empty pod ^s	1,191 ns	3,144 *	1,031 ns	84,09	23,61
Seed number	0,310 ns	2,300 ns	0,635 ns	81,65	41,88
Seed weight	0,563 ns	1,578 ns	1,036 ns	89,49	25,39
100 seed weight	1,327 ns	3,237 *	2,132 ns	34,98	18,27
Shoot fresh weight	1,533 ns	1,421 ns	0,575 ns	90,28	33,08
Root fresh weight	1,178 ns	1,774 ns	1,097 ns	49,01	20,35
Shoot dry weight	1,244 ns	0,344 ns	0,507 ns	60,57	20,81
Root dry weight	0,967 ns	2,335 ns	0,108 ns	43,10	14,28
Harvest period	2,849 *	3,166 *	6,678 **	4,71	
Pod weight/plot	0,434 ns	1,486 ns	1,066 ns	89,92	46,40

Note: ns = no significant effect, * = significant effect, ** = very significant effect, and t = transformation data [$\sqrt{(x+0.5)}$ or $\sqrt{(x+1)}$]

Combination Effect of Varieties and Vermicompost on Soybean Harvest Period

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Table 2. The combination effect of Soybean Varieties and Vermicompost Dosage on the Soybean Harvest period

Varieties	Vermicompost dosage			
	P0 (0 ton/ha)	P1 (5 ton/ha)	P2 (10 ton/ha)	P3 (15 ton/ha)
Detap 1	82.67 a A	85.33 b A	83.67 b A	86.33 b A
Devon 1	85.00 a B	95.33 a A	89.33 ab B	86.67 b B
Gepak Kuning	79.33 a B	89.00 ab AB	94.00 a A	86.00 b AB
Dering 1	84.33 a A	85.00 b A	91.33 ab A	94.67 a A

Note: Treatment means followed by the same capital letters at the same row are not significant, and by the same lowercase letters at the same column are not significant.

The finding of the study showed that soybeans fertilized with vermicompost generated a longer harvest period. The Detap-1 variety treated with vermicompost at a 5 tons/ha dose had a longer harvest period of 2.66 days than the non-fertilized variety. In contrast, the Devon 1 variety at the same dose had a more extended harvest period of 10.33 days. The unfertilized Gepak Kuning variety had a harvest period of 79.33 HST, while that fertilized with 10 tons/ha of vermicompost had a harvest period of 94 HST.

All soybean varieties fertilized with vermicompost, namely Detap 1, Devon 1, Gepak Kuning, and Dering 1, produced a longer harvest period than untreated ones. The Devon 1 and Gepak Kuning varieties responded better to vermicompost than the others. Compared to doses of 10 tons/ha and 15 tons/ha for the Devon 1 variety, applying vermicompost at a rate of 5 tons/ha resulted in a longer harvest period. On the other hand, the Gepak Kuning variety, which was fertilized with vermicompost at a dose of 10 tons/ha, yielded a longer harvest period than the 5 tons/ha and 15 tons/ha treatments. A higher harvest period increases plant productivity.

According to Egli (1999), plant morphophysiological characteristics, such as leaf thickness and plant growth rate, affect the process of photosynthesis, increasing plant productivity. A high seed filling rate and a relatively long duration will result in a high seed weight as long as the seed, as a sink, can accommodate the assimilates. In contrast, if the number of sinks is adequate, but the assimilate production is low, the result is empty seeds. Source limitations frequently arise during seed-filling, whereas sink limitations occur in non-stressed circumstances.

Soybean Growth and Yield Under Different Varieties

Several varieties of soybeans grown in coastal areas exhibited significant differences in pods/plants, empty pods, the weight of 100 seeds, and harvest time.

Table 3. Growth and yield of soybean in different varieties

Varieties	PH (cm)	LN	BN	PBN	PN	EP	SN	SW (g)
Detap 1	39.92	9.77	3.15	1.08	8.98 b	0.68 b	18.82	1.60
Devon 1	37.13	8.95	4.12	1.09	9.94 b	1.61 ab	15.34	0.80
Gepak Kuning	33.96	11.33	4.77	2.27	19.73 a	1.45 ab	34.63	1.81
During 1	38.14	10.50	3.62	1.55	15.16 ab	2.14 a	26.58	1.70

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Table 3 continued

Varieties	S100 (g)	SFW (g)	RFW (g)	SDW (g)	RDW (g)	HT	PW (g)
Detap 1	7.61 a	4.97	2.23	2.39	0.97	84.50 b	25.67
Devon 1	4.72 b	5.67	3.45	2.73	1.37	89.08 a	13.08
Gepak Kuning	5.51 b	9.75	2,52	2.67	0.96	87.08 ab	29.54
Dering 1	5.26 b	7.00	3.09	3.18	1.34	88.83 a	28.57

Note: Numbers followed by different letters in the same column are significantly different DMRT 5%. Plant Height (PH), Leaves Number (LN), Branches Number (BN), Productive Branches Number (PBN), Pods Number (PN), Empty Pods (EP), Seeds Number (SN), Seed Weight (SW), 100 seed weight (S100), Shoot Fresh Weight (SFW), Root Wet Weight (RWF), Shoot Dry Weight (SDW), Root Dry Weight (RDW), Harvest Time (HT), and Pod Weight (PW).

The Gepak Kuning variety produced more soybean pods (19.73 pods) than the Detap 1 varieties (8.98 pods) and Devon 1 varieties (9.94 pods). The number of pods indicates that the Gepak Kuning variety is a soybean variety with the advantage of being drought tolerant due to the high number of pods produced per plant. Dering 1 is a drought-tolerant variety with small seed sizes. Meanwhile, cultivars that are not drought tolerant, namely Detap 1 and Devon 1, have lower soybean yields than Gepak Kuning, which is drought tolerant. Detap 1 has 0.68 empty pods, less than Dering 1 (2.14 pods). The few empty pods indicated that Detap 1 was tolerant to soybean pod-sucking insects. The highest weight of 100 seeds was produced by Detap 1 (7.61 g), followed by Gepak Kuning (5.51 g), Devon 1 (4.72 g), and Dering 1 (5.26 g). Based on the description of the variety, Detap 1 has the heaviest weight of 100 seeds compared to other varieties. Nevertheless, the study showed that the weight of 100 seeds did not meet the potential weight of 100 seeds based on the variety description. Detap 1 was harvested four days earlier (84.5 WAP) than Dering 1 (88.83 WAP) and five days earlier than Devon 1 (89.08 WAP). Based on harvest time, the results showed that the four varieties grown on coastal land had a longer harvest period than the variety description.

Lower water-receiving plants will grow worse than that sufficient ones. Water shortages can severely affect crop yield and even cause plant death (Nio and Banyo, 2011). Plant productivity (biomass) is reduced when water is scarce due to decreased primary metabolic activity, photosynthesis, and reduced leaf area. The reduction in biomass accumulation due to water scarcity varies depending on the plant's response to water shortage (Solichatun et al., 2005).

According to Liebig's minimum law, natural plants face ecological variables such as biotic and abiotic factors. Under certain conditions, environmental factors can limit plant growth and yield (Mukharomah, 2021). In this study, drought stress conditions in coastal land might have been the limiting factors for the growth and yield of soybeans. Aside from drought stress, the low availability of N in the study might be another reason. Low K content is also a limiting factor for soybean growth and development in coastal areas. According to Munawar (2011), crop yield highly depends on the lowest essential nutrient. A limited amount of nutrients will be a limiting factor for plant growth and yield.

At the beginning of the plant growth, the water availability was lower than the soybean water requirement, indicated by lower rainfall in July. Rainfall increased from August to October and was within the normal range for soybean growth. Nevertheless, one of the issues with sandy soil is its high porosity, which limits its ability to hold water. According to Yuwono (2009), coastal land is marginal land with a sandy texture, loose structure, low nutrient content, low cation exchange capacity, low water holding capacity, high daytime soil temperature, high wind speed, and very high evaporation rate. The main problem of dry land is a lack of water, which disrupts plant photosynthesis and causes a decrease in N concentration in dry plant tissue (Chen et al., 2015; Sopandie, 2013).

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Plant morphophysiological characteristics, such as leaf thickness and plant growth rate, influence plant productivity because they affect the rate of photosynthesis. As long as the seed can accumulate the assimilates, a high seed weight will result from a high seed filling rate in a relatively long duration. If there are enough sinks, but the assimilation produced is low, it will result in empty seeds (Egli, 1999). The soybean yields of Detap 1, Devon 1, Gepak Kuning, and Dering varieties were 171.33 kg/ha, 87.2 kg/ha, 196.93 kg/ha, and 190.46 kg/ha, respectively. These results indicate that the Detap 1, Devon 1, Gepak Kuning, and Dering 1 variety has lower productivity than their potential when grown in coastal areas.

Effect of Vermicompost on Soybean Growth and Yield

Applying different doses of vermicompost to soybeans in coastal areas significantly affected harvest time but did not affect soybean growth or yield variables (Table 5).

Table 4. Effect of vermicompost dosage on soybean growth and yield

Dosage (ton/Ha)	PH	LN	BN	PBN	PN	EP	SN
0	39.27	10.42	3.85	1.73	15.18	1.10	29.57
5	38.41	11.02	4.05	1.68	14.83	1.50	24.68
10	37.58	9.47	3.57	1.21	12.22	2.00	19.71
15	33.89	9.65	4.18	1.38	11.60	1.28	21.40

Tabel 4....cont....

Dosage (ton/Ha)	SW (g)	S100 (g)	SFW (g)	RFW (g)	SDW (g)	RDW (g)	HT (g)	PW (g)
0	2.01	6.88	7.04	3.01	3.23	1.15	82.83 b	32.52
5	1.49	6.06	7.11	3.29	2.77	1.24	88.66 a	25.19
10	1.14	4.96	4.94	2.74	2.55	1.14	89.58 a	18.93
15	1.26	5.22	8.30	2.24	2.42	1.11	88.41 a	20.23

Note: Numbers followed by different letters in the same column are significantly different at LSD 5%. Plant Height (PH), Leaves Number (LN), Branches Number (BN), Productive Branches Number (PBN), Pods Number (PN), Empty Pods (EP), Seeds Number (JBP), Seed Weight (SW), 100 seed weight (S100), Shoot Fresh Weight (SFW), Root Wet Weight (RWF), Shoot Dry Weight (SDW), Root Dry Weight (RDW), Harvest Time (HT), and Pod Weight (PW).

Table 4 shows that unfertilized soybeans had a shorter harvest time than vermicompost-fertilized soybeans. The harvest period for the control treatment (no fertilization) was 82.83 WAP, whereas those fertilized with vermicompost harvested between 88.41 and 89.98 WAP. One of the functions of fertilizer is to supply available nutrients to the soil. Fertilizer is a material added to the soil or plant canopy to supplement nutrients (Surbakti et al., 2013). Vermicompost contains humic acid in addition to nutrients. Humic compounds and clay are involved in several chemical processes in the soil. Vermicompost has high CEC due to its content of humic acid. The CEC of vermicompost ranges from 35 me/100g to 130 me/100g. Thus, vermicompost can supply nutrients and increase soil fertility (Nasution et al., 2013).

Soybean yields were not significantly different between unfertilized and fertilized with vermicompost and were lower than their yield potential. The low yield of soybeans on vermicompost-fertilized coastal land indicates that applying vermicompost at a dose of 15 tons/ha was ineffective in increasing soybean growth and yield; therefore, the dose should be increased. Poor soybean growth and yield might have been associated with insufficient vermicompost applied. The soil in the experiment site had a pH of 5.93 (slightly acidic), C-Organic 6.13 (very high), N -total 0.04 (very low), and a sandy texture (91.32%), dust (1.95%), and clay (6.73%)., indicating low soil fertility.

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According to Sumardi (2008), coastal land generally has unstable soil properties, low soil moisture, high evapotranspiration, high salinity, and low organic matter content. The vermicompost used in this study had pH = 7.31, C-Organic = 26.16 %, N = 1.65 %, C/N ratio = 15.87, P = 1.08 %, K = 2.04 % , and water content = 27.04%. However, the research findings revealed that applying vermicompost up to 15 ton/ha did not increase soybean yield. Low nutrient and water content in the experimental site limited the soybean growth and yield. According to Liebig's law, plant growth depends on biotic and abiotic ecological factors, where the minimum level is the most prominent factor (Mukharomah, 2021).

CONCLUSIONS

The Devon 1 variety fertilized with Vermicompost 5 tons/ha exhibited the longest soybean harvest time, followed by the Gepak Kuning fertilized with Vermicompost 10 tons/ha. The highest soybean yields were produced by the Gepak Kuning, followed by Dering 1, Detap 1, and Devon 1. Applying vermicompost prolongs the harvest time for soybeans grown in coastal areas.

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